

**TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF JOB SATISFACTION
AMONG DIFFERENT FACULTIES OF A UNIVERSITY
IN JILIN PROVINCE, CHINA**

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Abstract:

The present study sought to discover teachers' perceptions of their job satisfaction based on the demographic characteristics of *gender*, *age* and *faculty* at one university in Jilin province, China. The study used quantitative research method. The sample of the study comprised of 116 participants from eight different faculties in the university. Out of this, 62 were males and 54 were females. The questionnaire instrument used was based on a 5 point-Likert scale from *Strongly Disagree 1, Disagree 2, Neutral 3, Agree 4 and Strongly Agree 5*. All the items in the questionnaire tested job satisfaction aspects of the faculty members. The data was analysed by the use of the descriptive statistics using Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) software. An analysis of the data by use of ANOVA revealed a significant difference in job satisfaction between the *faculties*. For the independent variable of *age*, ANOVA analysis showed that there was no significant difference in job satisfaction between the age groups. As far as the third independent variable of *gender* was concerned, the result showed that there was no significant difference between males and females in job satisfaction of the teachers in the university. The study was guided by Herzberg (1959) Motivational Hygiene theory. Herzberg believes that employees tend to be motivated by factors like personal advancement, achievement & development, responsibility and recognition in the execution of their duties.

Keywords: teachers' perceptions, job satisfaction, faculties, age, gender

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1. Introduction

In the past, job satisfaction among different employees has received a lot of attention from many scholars. For instance, Liu L. et al (2015) stated that studies on job satisfaction and working condition among faculty members have become an essential issue in the institutions of higher learning recently. Employers, government institutions and other stake holders in any organization or institution who happen to hire employees should at all times strive to know whether their workers have some level of job satisfaction. By being familiar with the job satisfaction of a worker, the employer would be able to seek a useful information and ways of how to motivate his or her workers. A motivated worker is generally known to be enthusiastic, happy and willing to perform his or her duties diligently (Toker B. 2011). When duties assigned to a worker are done to perfection, then the result is always good, acceptable and satisfactory. To achieve this goal of motivating one's workers, one has to check and carry out an assessment of the job satisfactions of the concerned workers. (Ghenghesh, 2013, p. 457) mentioned *"Motivation is considered to be the driving force behind all actions performed and is thought to be responsible for why and how people decide to do something"*.

2. Literature Review

In my attempt to review various literature available on job satisfaction, I have come across some studies that have so far been conducted in this area which are already available in the body of knowledge. Some of these studies that were conducted on universities' teaching staff job satisfaction include :Al-Smadi et al. (2015), Bozeman, et al. (2011), Filiz (2014), Lai et al. (2010), Ssesanga, et al. (2005) and Castillo, et al. (2004). Most of these studies have shed more light on the job satisfaction of the academic staff in the universities under study. The studies have also shown the level of the job satisfaction as well as the significance of carrying out a research in this area in general. Some independent variables like the demographic characteristics of age and gender of some studies have been found to have had either an impact or no impact on the overall level of job satisfaction. *"The survey reveals that demographic factors such as age, academic rank, and degree had no significant impact on job satisfaction. Nonetheless, demographic characteristics facilitated the discovery of differences in overall job satisfaction by gender"*, (Malik, 2011, p. 270). The different studies conducted in this area of job satisfaction had always reported different or the same results depending on where, how and when the studies have been carried out. For example, Liu et al. (2015) found out that males had higher job satisfaction scores than females.

Theoretically, Herzberg (1959) Motivational Hygiene theory has guided this study. In his theory, Herzberg asserted that employees would usually try to acquire 'hygiene needs' like work conditions, policy, relationship with supervisor, security and status since they feel not joyful without them. But once the individuals are satisfied, the hygiene influence slowly fades away since satisfaction itself is regarded as temporary. It is therefore necessary for the employers and managers to understand that their employees are not necessarily motivated by 'hygiene needs'. Herzberg therefore believes that employees tend to be motivated by factors like personal advancement, achievement and development. He further mentioned that recognition, responsibility and work itself are other real motivators or satisfiers in the job market.

The present study had therefore sought to find out the teachers' perception of their job satisfaction based on the demographic characteristics of gender, age and faculty at one university in Jilin province, China. Based on the above background, the present study has specifically been guided by the following research question and hypothesis:

3. Research Question

"What are the teachers' perceptions of their job satisfaction based on the demographic characteristics of Gender, Age and Faculty?"

3.1 Hypothesis

There would be a significant difference in job satisfaction between gender, the four age groups and the faculties.

4. Methods

The study adopted quantitative research methods. The sample of the study comprised of 116 participants from eight different faculties of the university. Out of this, 62 were males and 54 were females. The age of the participants were grouped into four (Those less than 30 years of age, 31-40, 41-50 and above 50 years). The instrument used was a Likert Scale type of questionnaire comprising of 25 items as well as the demographic information of the participants (gender, age and faculty). The questionnaire instrument was based on a 5 point-Likert scale from *Strongly Disagree 1, Disagree 2, Neutral 3, Agree 4 and Strongly Agree 5*. All the items in the questionnaire tested job satisfaction aspects of the faculty members like salaries, job securities, teaching and learning environment,

promotions and social status. The data was analysed by the use of descriptive statistics using Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) software. From there two tests were used, independent sample-t test and one-way ANOVA to determine the job satisfaction difference among *gender*, *age* and *faculty* of the participants.

5. Results and Discussions

		Faculty	Gender	Age	Satisfaction
N	Valid	116	116	106	104
	Missing	0	0	10	12
Mean		4.14	1.47	2.33	90.03
Median		4.00	1.00	2.00	89.00
Std. Deviation		2.428	.501	.943	14.120
Minimum		1	1	1	45
Maximum		8	2	4	125

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of satisfaction based on faculty, gender and age

A descriptive analysis of the data has shown a minimum satisfaction level of 45 and a maximum satisfaction level of 125, a mean satisfaction of 90.03 and a standard deviation of 14.120.

ANOVA for *faculties*

Satisfaction

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3660.881	7	522.983	2.975	.007
Within Groups	16876.032	96	175.792		
Total	20536.913	103			

Table 2: An analysis of satisfaction by faculty using ANOVA

An analysis of the data by use of ANOVA revealed a significant difference in job satisfaction between the faculties as far as the independent variable of *Faculty* was concerned ($F(7, 96) = 2.975, p = 0.007$). A further analysis of post hoc showed that teachers in the faculty of physics had a higher job satisfaction than those in the faculty of geography ($p = 0.001$).

It is worth noting that the post hoc multiple comparisons results among faculties' mean difference was significant at the 0.005 level.

ANOVA for age

Satisfaction

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	289.284	3	96.428	.464	.708
Within Groups	18707.152	90	207.857		
Total	18996.436	93			

Table 3: An analysis of satisfaction by age using ANOVA

For the independent variable of *age*, ANOVA analysis showed that there was no significant difference in job satisfaction between the age groups, $F(3, 90) = .464$, $p = .708$.

4.1 Independent T-Test for gender

Independent Samples Test

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	.077	.782	1.591	102	.115	4.387	2.757	-1.082	9.856
Equal variances not assumed			1.594	100.300	.114	4.387	2.752	-1.072	9.846

Table 4: An analysis of satisfaction by gender using independent samples t-test

The third independent variable of the study was *gender*. Independent sample t-test was used to analyse the job satisfaction difference of the teachers on the basis of gender. The result showed that there was no significant difference between males and females in job satisfaction, $t(102) = 1.591$, $p = 0.115$.

Generally, the teachers surveyed in the faculties were satisfied with their job. This means that the conditions under which they work are quite favourable. Since the questionnaire items tested almost all the aspects of the teachers' job satisfaction like salaries, job securities, teaching and learning environment, promotions and social

status, it can be concluded that the teachers in the eight faculties were actually satisfied with their job. Three independent variables guided the study i.e. *faculty, gender and age*. There was a significant difference in job satisfaction between the faculties of Physics and that of Geography. Faculty of Physics had a high job satisfaction compared to that of Geography, this can mainly be attributed to the difference in salaries since the different faculties remunerate their members differently. As far as the gender is concerned, there was no significant difference in job satisfaction based on gender. This means that both males and females had the same level of job satisfaction in the university. This study therefore has contradicted the findings of Liu et al. (2015) which found out that males had higher job satisfaction scores than females. The other independent variable was age, where again the results showed that there was no significant difference in job satisfaction based on age of the participants in the study. This can be attributed to the fact that the faculties treat their members equally regardless of the age of the member hence no difference in satisfaction level. This study was in tandem with that of Malik (2011) which found out that demographic characteristics like age had no significant impact on the job satisfaction of the faculty members.

5. Conclusion

This study sought to find out the perceptions of teachers on their job satisfaction in the different faculties of one university in Jilin province, China. Faculty, age and gender were the three independent variables of the study. It was found out that the teachers surveyed in the faculties were satisfied with their job. This therefore meant that the conditions under which they worked were quite favourable

6. Recommendations

It is recommended that a further study of the same nature to aught be conducted in at least three universities in North-eastern China to expand the scope and the generalization of this study in English language.

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